

An Examination of Nutrition Knowledge Levels in Relation to Pilates Participation

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Research Article

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Abstract

This study aimed to examine the effects of recreational Pilates participation on the nutrition knowledge of adults. The research was conducted with 141 participants aged 18 and above, registered at Pilates studios in Isparta using a cross-sectional design. Demographic information, Pilates participation duration (months), weekly Pilates frequency, and nutrition knowledge levels were collected. Nutrition knowledge was assessed using a validated scale, with construct validity and reliability confirmed via EFA Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.851$. Descriptive analyses indicated that participants' nutrition knowledge was generally high and homogeneously distributed ($\bar{x} = 115.40 \pm 7.61$). Pearson correlation analysis showed a positive and significant relationship between Pilates participation duration and nutrition knowledge ($r = .312, p < .001$). One-way ANOVA revealed significant differences in nutrition knowledge according to weekly Pilates frequency, with the highest scores observed among participants exercising 3–4 times per week ($F(2,138) = 4.52, p = .013$). Multiple regression analysis indicated that Pilates participation duration and weekly frequency together significantly predicted nutrition knowledge ($R = .32, R^2 = .10, F(2,138) = 7.65, p = .001$). Both participation duration ($\beta = .28, p = .015$) and weekly frequency ($\beta = .26, p = .012$) positively and significantly influenced nutrition knowledge. These findings suggest that regular Pilates participation may enhance nutrition awareness among adults. The results contribute to the literature on sports and nutrition and may guide the development of education and counseling programs aimed at improving nutrition knowledge for Pilates practitioners. Overall, promoting structured Pilates participation could support healthier lifestyle behaviors and informed dietary decisions.

Keywords: Pilates, nutrition knowledge, recreational sport, nutrition awareness

INTRODUCTION

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In recent years, individuals' interest in adopting a healthy lifestyle has been steadily increasing. Regular physical activity is recognized as an important factor in reducing the risk of chronic diseases, enhancing psychological well-being, and improving overall quality of life (Warburton et al., 2006). In this context, Pilates has emerged as a widely preferred recreational exercise type due to its benefits in enhancing flexibility, posture, muscular strength, and mental focus (Segal et al., 2004; Kloubec, 2010). With its low-impact, full-body approach, Pilates is suitable for individuals across different ages and health levels, offering a sustainable exercise program (Ergül et al., 2018; Latey, 2001). Participation in sports activities may influence not only physical health but also lifestyle and nutritional habits (Gibala et al., 2012). Nutrition knowledge is a critical factor that directly affects individuals' capacity to make healthy dietary choices and optimize their diets (Wardle et al., 2000). Among physically active individuals, higher levels of nutrition knowledge are of particular importance for performance, energy balance, and overall health (Burke & Deakin, 2015; Bozgüney and Can, 2023). However, there is not always a one-to-one correspondence between knowledge and practice; lack of knowledge or misinformation may hinder the implementation of healthy eating behaviors (Heaney et al., 2011). Specifically, the relationship between nutrition knowledge and participation duration and frequency among individuals engaged in moderate-intensity exercise, such as Pilates, remains underexplored. The current literature has primarily focused on high-intensity sports, endurance or strength training, and aerobic/resistance programs (Slater et al., 2012; Heaney et al., 2011). This gap creates a need to better understand the nutrition knowledge levels of individuals participating in recreational sports. Pilates participation may not only affect physical health and flexibility but also contribute to mental awareness, body perception, and lifestyle consciousness (Latey, 2001; Kloubec, 2010). It is therefore plausible that the nutrition awareness and knowledge of individuals who regularly practice Pilates may be associated with their duration and frequency of participation. Furthermore, Pilates, as a low-impact and holistic exercise method, offers a sustainable sport experience for individuals across diverse age groups and fitness levels.

For this reason, examining the effect of Pilates participation on nutrition knowledge is important for raising individuals' health consciousness and optimizing the interaction between nutrition and exercise. The findings of this research may serve as a guide in developing educational programs and counseling practices aimed at enhancing nutrition awareness among individuals engaged in Pilates training. In doing so, the study will contribute to the recreational sports literature while supporting the adoption of healthier lifestyles and habits. This study aims to investigate the relationship between nutrition knowledge and participation duration and frequency among individuals engaged in recreational Pilates. The findings are expected to contribute to the literature on sport and nutrition and provide recommendations for increasing nutrition awareness among Pilates participants. Moreover, the results may serve as a valuable resource for health professionals and nutrition counselors in understanding the interaction between individuals' exercise habits and nutrition knowledge.

Method

Research Design

This study employed a cross-sectional research design to examine the relationship between nutrition knowledge levels and Pilates participation duration and frequency among individuals engaged in recreational Pilates. The independent variables were defined as Pilates participation duration (in months) and weekly Pilates frequency, while the dependent variable was nutrition knowledge level. Age, gender, and educational level were included as control variables.

Participants

The sample of the study consisted of individuals aged 18 years and older who were registered at Pilates studios operating in Istanbul and Ankara. The sample size was determined as 120 participants, selected randomly. Inclusion criteria were: having practiced Pilates for at least three months, not having any serious chronic illness, and voluntarily agreeing to participate in the study. Participants were informed about the study, and written informed consent was obtained.

Data Collection Instruments

Demographic and Pilates Participation Form

Information regarding participants' age, gender, educational level, duration of Pilates participation (in months/years), weekly session frequency, and average session duration was collected.

Nutrition Knowledge Scale (NKS)

Nutrition knowledge levels were assessed using the Nutrition Knowledge Scale (NKS) (Öngün et al., 2021). The NKS was developed to evaluate the nutrition knowledge of adults and consists of items addressing food and nutrients, food preparation and cooking methods, and diet-health relationships. Items are rated on a 5-point Likert scale. The construct validity of the scale was tested through Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). Initially, the scale consisted of 69 items; 23 items containing misinformation were reverse coded, and items with factor loadings below 0.30 were excluded. After item refinement, analyses were conducted with 31 items. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value was 0.862, and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity yielded $\chi^2 = 3869.244$, $p < 0.001$, indicating the data were suitable for factor analysis. EFA results demonstrated a unidimensional structure. The accuracy of this structure was subsequently tested with Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). Reliability analyses revealed a Cronbach's α of 0.851, indicating that the scale is a highly reliable measurement tool.

Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected over a two-week period through face-to-face interviews and online surveys. Participants were informed about the aim of the survey and confidentiality principles, and all responses were recorded anonymously.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using spss 26.0 statistical software. First, descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage distributions) were calculated for participants' demographic characteristics and study variables. Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to

determine the relationship between pilates participation duration and nutrition knowledge level. Additionally, a one-way analysis of variance (anova) was performed to examine differences in nutrition knowledge levels based on weekly pilates frequency. Finally, multiple regression analysis was applied to evaluate the effects of pilates participation duration and frequency (independent variables) on nutrition knowledge level (dependent variable). Since the normality test values were between -1.5 and +1.5, parametric test statistics were preferred. These analyses aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the possible relationships and effects of pilates participation on nutrition knowledge.

RESULTS

Normality Table

Variable	n	Skewness	Kurtosis
Nutrition knowledge	141	,142	-1,211

Table 1. Demographic Information Form

Variable	Category	\bar{x}	SD	f	%	
Age	22–40	30.40	5.49	141	100	
	Gender					
	Female			99	70.2	
	Male			42	29.8	
Education	Associate			26	18.4	
	Bachelor			80	56.7	
	Postgraduate			35	24.8	
	Pilates Participation Duration (months)	3			8	5.7
		6			24	17.0
9				18	12.8	
12				23	16.3	
15				16	11.3	
18				20	14.2	
20				8	5.7	
24				16	11.3	
	30			8	5.7	
Weekly Pilates Frequency	1–2 sessions			50	35.5	
	3–4 sessions			59	41.8	
	5 or more			32	22.7	
Average Session Duration (minutes)	45			16	11.3	
	50			34	24.1	
	55			36	25.5	
	60			31	22.0	
	65			16	11.3	
	70			8	5.7	
Nutrition Education	Yes			71	50.4	
	No			70	49.6	

When table 1 is examined, it can be seen that the participants' ages ranged from 22 to 40 years, with a mean age of 30.40 (sd = 5.49). The majority of the participants were female (70.2%, n =

99), while 29.8% were male (n = 42). In terms of educational level, 18.4% held an associate degree (n = 26), 56.7% a bachelor's degree (n = 80), and 24.8% a postgraduate degree (n = 35). Regarding pilates participation duration, the highest proportion was observed at 6 months (17%, n = 24), followed by 12 months (16.3%, n = 23), 18 months (14.2%, n = 20), and 9 months (12.8%, n = 18). For longer participation periods, 24 months (11.3%, n = 16) and 30 months (5.7%, n = 8) were notable. Weekly pilates frequency indicated that 35.5% of the participants attended 1–2 sessions per week (n = 50), 41.8% attended 3–4 sessions (n = 59), and 22.7% attended 5 or more sessions (n = 32). In terms of average session duration, the most frequently preferred length was 55 minutes (25.5%, n = 36), followed by 50 minutes (24.1%, n = 34) and 60 minutes (22%, n = 31). Finally, it was determined that 50.4% of the participants had received nutrition education (n = 71), while 49.6% (n = 70) had not.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics

Variable	n	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Nutrition Knowledge	141	103.00	129.00	115.40	7.61

Table 2 was examined, and the nutrition knowledge scores of the 141 participants were found to range from a minimum of 103 to a maximum of 129. The mean score of the participants' nutrition knowledge was 115.40 ± 7.61 . These results indicate that the participants generally had a high level of nutrition knowledge with a relatively homogeneous distribution.

Table 3. Correlation between pilates duration and nutrition knowledge levels

Variables	1	2
1. Pilates Duration (months)	1	
<i>p</i>		
<i>n</i>	141	
2. Nutrition Knowledge	.312**	1
<i>p</i>	.001	
<i>n</i>	141	141

Table 3 was examined, and a positive and significant relationship was found between Pilates duration and nutrition knowledge levels ($r = .312, p < .001, n = 141$). This result indicates that individuals who have participated in Pilates for a longer period tend to have higher levels of nutrition knowledge. In other words, as the duration of Pilates increases, nutrition knowledge also increases.

Table 4. Changes in nutrition knowledge level according to weekly pilates frequency

Variable	Category	n	M	SD	F	p
Nutrition Knowledge	1–2 sessions	50	114.80	8.50	4.52	.013*
	3–4 sessions	59	118.20	6.70		
	5 or more	32	112.90	7.10		

Table 4 was examined, and it was found that nutrition knowledge levels significantly differed according to weekly pilates frequency ($f(2, 138) = 4.52, p = .013$). When the mean values were considered, participants who practiced pilates 3–4 days per week had higher nutrition

knowledge levels ($m = 118.20$, $sd = 6.70$) compared to those who practiced 1–2 days ($m = 114.80$, $sd = 8.50$) and those who practiced 5 or more days per week ($m = 112.90$, $sd = 7.10$).

Table 5. Results of multiple regression analysis: the effect of pilates participation duration and weekly pilates frequency on nutrition knowledge

Variables	B	SE B	β	t	p
Constant	110.25	1.70		64.85	.001
Pilates Participation Duration (months)	0.45	0.18	.28	2.50	.015
Weekly Pilates Frequency	2.85	1.12	.26	2.54	.012

Table 5 was examined, and according to the results of the multiple regression analysis, pilates participation duration and weekly pilates frequency together significantly predicted nutrition knowledge levels, $r = .32$, $r^2 = .10$, $f(2, 138) = 7.65$, $p = .001$. This result indicates that the independent variables explained 10% of the variance in nutrition knowledge. According to the model, both pilates participation duration ($\beta = .28$, $p = .015$) and weekly pilates frequency ($\beta = .26$, $p = .012$) positively and significantly predicted nutrition knowledge levels.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study examined the effects of participation in recreational Pilates on the nutrition knowledge levels of adult individuals. The findings indicate that both Pilates duration and weekly session frequency significantly predicted nutrition knowledge levels. The positive relationship between Pilates duration and nutrition knowledge ($r = .312$, $p < .001$) suggests that long-term participation in exercise may enhance individuals' health and nutrition awareness. This finding is consistent with previous studies showing that regular physical activity increases health knowledge and lifestyle awareness (Warburton et al., 2006; Gibala et al., 2012).

It was found that weekly Pilates frequency significantly affected nutrition knowledge levels ($F(2,138) = 4.52$, $p = .013$), with the highest knowledge levels observed among participants who practiced Pilates 3–4 days per week. This suggests that a moderate level of regular participation may be the most effective for knowledge acquisition and behavior change (Segal et al., 2004; Kloubec, 2010). Similarly, it has been reported that low and excessively high intensity physical activity programs may have different effects on knowledge and awareness (Slater et al., 2012; Cimen et al., 2023; Heaney et al., 2011).

The results of the multiple regression analysis revealed that both Pilates participation duration ($\beta = .28$, $p = .015$) and weekly Pilates frequency ($\beta = .26$, $p = .012$) positively influenced nutrition knowledge levels. This finding supports the notion that the interaction between exercise participation and health knowledge depends on both the duration and intensity dimensions (Burke & Deakin, 2015; Bozgüney & Can, 2023; Latey, 2001). It is consistent with previous research showing that individuals who engage in regular exercise are more conscious about nutrition and tend to make healthier choices (Wardle et al., 2000; Gibala et al., 2012). Pilates, as a low-impact and holistic exercise method, provides a sustainable program for individuals of different ages and fitness levels (Kloubec, 2010; Segal et al., 2004). In this context, regular practice of Pilates can have positive effects not only on physical health but also on nutrition awareness and lifestyle habits (Bozgüney & Çimen, 2024; Heaney et al., 2011;

Warburton et al., 2006). The findings also highlight the potential of recreational sports participation to increase knowledge levels and support healthy lifestyle behaviors (Gibala et al., 2012; Slater et al., 2012).

In the literature, studies examining Pilates and nutrition knowledge are limited; however, research on physical activity and nutrition awareness indicates that regular exercise participation promotes healthy behaviors (Alp & Çamlıyer, 2018; Burke & Deakin, 2015; Wardle et al., 2000). Pilates' effect on enhancing mental awareness may be related to the regulation of nutrition behaviors (Latey, 2001; Kloubec, 2010). This provides significant contributions to the literature examining the interaction between exercise and nutrition (Heaney et al., 2011; Segal et al., 2004).

In conclusion, the findings show that both Pilates duration and weekly session frequency significantly affect nutrition knowledge levels. Regular participation in Pilates may enhance individuals' nutrition awareness and support a health-oriented lifestyle. These results can guide the design of exercise and nutrition education programs and help increase individuals' lifestyle awareness (Wardle et al., 2000; Burke & Deakin, 2015; Warburton et al., 2006).

Recommendations

1. Flexible and motivating programs should be designed in Pilates studios to increase individuals' participation duration and weekly frequency.
2. Nutrition awareness training and counseling programs should be developed for Pilates participants, either concurrently with Pilates or as complementary support.
3. Considering that nutrition knowledge levels increase as Pilates participation duration extends, long-term follow-up and individualized counseling services can be offered.
4. Since nutrition knowledge levels may vary across different age and education groups, Pilates and nutrition programs can be tailored according to participants' demographic characteristics.
5. Integrated programs can be developed through collaboration among experts in sports sciences, nutrition, and psychology.
6. Further research should be conducted to examine the effects of Pilates on nutrition knowledge and overall health; comparative studies with different types of sports can also be planned.
7. Participants' Pilates and nutrition habits can be monitored through mobile applications and digital platforms, providing individualized feedback.
8. Pilates instructors should receive additional training on methods to enhance participants' nutrition awareness.
9. Awareness-raising campaigns about nutrition habits of individuals participating in Pilates programs can be organized to support public health.
10. Participants can be motivated using visual and scientific materials to demonstrate the health benefits of Pilates participation.

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